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Predictors Of And Experiences Of Non-Consensual Sex Among Public Senior Secondary School Students In Ogbia Local Government Area Of Bayelsa State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the predictors and experiences of non-consensual sex among senior secondary school students in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State, Nigeria using a descriptive survey design, the population of the study consisted of 4933 public senior secondary school students between the ages of 12-20 years. A sample size of 440 was derived using a Taro Yamane formula. Data was collected using a structured self-administered questionnaire with close ended questions. Seven research questions and seven hypotheses guided the study. Data analysis was done using descriptive statistics of simple percentage and frequencies to answer the research questions while Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05. The findings of the study showed 95(75.4%) of the respondents aged 12-17 years experienced non-consensual sex, more females 121(66.5%) experienced non-consensual sex, 153(46.2%) of the respondents who were pressured experienced non-consensual sex, more of the respondents 92(43.4%) who lived in urban area experienced non-consensual sex, being in SS2 91(50.8%) was associated with experience of non-consensual sex, more of the respondents who were Christians 120(57.1%), and 33(22.0%) of Muslim experienced non-consensual sex, those without sexual orientation 62(41.1%) had more experience of non-consensual sex. The findings also indicate a significant relationship between gender, peer pressure, place of residence, student's class, religion, sexual orientation and experiences of non-consensual sex among senior secondary schools students in Bayelsa State ($p < 0.05$). Based on the findings of the study it was recommended that government, education authorities and related health agencies should put in place measures to promote sex education, reproductive rights and responsibilities among young ones. It was concluded that younger age, female gender, peer pressure, place of residence, students' class, religion and sexual orientation are important predictors of non-consensual sex. Therefore, there is need to put in place special programmes that will address the perception and attitude towards non-consensual sex among young ones.

Keywords: non-consensual sex, senior secondary school students

INTRODUCTION

Non-consensual sex is a major problem that unreasonably affects young people in Nigeria specifically in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. Hence, any sexual activity that is done without the person's knowledge, permission, or consent is referred to as non-consensual sex. Forced sex, transactional sex, cross-generational sex, unwelcome touch, and sexual molestation are just a few examples of non-consensual sex. Unknown people, peer groups, close partners, family members, guardians, and powerful authorities can engage in non-consensual sex.

Non-consensual sex encounters started by sexual offenders include a variety of unnecessary sexual attempts or approaches including unnecessary touching of sensitive or erotic body parts like the penis, vulva, buttocks, thighs, breast, Arola, or nipple, ears, and neck, as well as making worthless sexual remarks, encircling the victim forcefully, kissing without permission, and using verbal or oral coercion. Furthermore, it is widely believed that men can touch, kiss, and coerce women into paying for sexual intercourse. Imaledo et al., (2012) research on perception of non-consensual sex relayed that it was wrong for a partner/girl or boy friend to beat his/her partner for refusing sexual contact, and that it is not right for a man to force his partner (girlfriend) to have sex with him. Further reports on reporting indicated that it was perceived as wrong for a man to report if he is forced to have sex by his girlfriend to the authority and that it is also not proper for the girl to report non-consensual sex either.

Sexual criminals, as indicated above, initiate non-consensual sex acts and encounters in a variety of settings, including homes, markets, streets, schools, and garages. When reported, incidents involving male colleagues touching female colleagues at the aforementioned erotic or erogenous parts of the body against their will have, in some cases, resulted in victimization either directly or indirectly, whereas incidents involving female colleagues touching male colleagues have, for the most part, not been reported. According to the New-Youth Policy (2019), youths in Nigeria include citizens of the Federal Republic of Nigeria aged 18 to 29. This explains why the NYSC program is only open to recent graduates under the age of 30. The African Youths Charter, on the other hand, defines youths as being between the ages of 15 and 35.

However, it has been observed that students in public senior secondary schools have been engaging into indiscriminate sexual activities in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State, with limited understanding and experiences of non-consensual sex. Indiscriminate sexual activities usually occur during burial ceremonies, in the parties, cultural ceremonies, and community festive period. Some students were seen with sexy dressing, and were indulge in smoking hard drugs such as Indian hemp, ice, and hero and others, some also indulge in excessive consumption of alcohol and the aforementioned hard drugs which motivated them to indiscriminate sexual activities, experiencing unwanted touching of erogenous areas of the body, sexual intimidation and coercion, Verbal harassment and repeated threats ,being forced to watch pornography, being drugged into having sex against their will, and other similar acts.

These unwanted sexual activities results in rape cases sometime students had the risk of contracting sexually transmitted diseases such as gonorrhoea, syphilis, hepatitis B, chancre, unplanned pregnancies, unsafe abortion, poor academic performance, dropout from school, fear of the sexual criminals, stress, inferiority complex and social isolation. On the other hand, students had engaged in unwanted sexual contact through experiential learning, with little to no awareness that these experiences are not consensual. They were also viewed unfavorably since non-consensual sex was assumed to be a harmless activity, despite the fact that it can have major health and psychological effects on them and even result in death in some situations.

Hence, there is need to examine the predictors and experiences of non-consensual sex among Public senior secondary school students in Ogbia Local Government Area Bayelsa State.

METHODOLOGY

The study was carried out among public senior secondary school students in Bayelsa State. The study adopted a descriptive cross-sectional survey design. The population of this study consisted of four thousand nine hundred and thirty three (4933) public senior secondary school students between the ages of 12 -20 years (Bayelsa State Senior Secondary School Board, Students Enrolment, 1st Term 2022-2023 session). The sample size of this study consisted of four hundred and forty (440) students' males/ females using Taro Yamene's Formula. The instrument for data collection was structured questionnaire titled; Predictors and experiences of Non-consensual Sex Questionnaire (PENCSQ). The instrument was validated and the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) was used to calculate a reliability coefficient of 0.81. Data collection was collected on one to one delivery of the instrument to the respondents. The collected data was analysed using descriptive statistics of simple percentage and frequencies to answer the demographic data and research questions while Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMCC) was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level.

RESULTS

Table 4.1: Socio-demographic Data

Variables	Frequency	Percentages
Age		
12 – 17	126	30.0
18 – 20	294	70.0
Gender		
Male	238	56.7
Female	182	43.3
Place of residence		
Yenagoa	212	50.5
Village	150	35.7
Water Front	58	13.8
Class		
SS1	183	43.6
SS2	179	42.6
SS3	58	13.8
Religion		
Christianity	210	50.0
Islam	150	35.7
Traditional African Religion	60	14.3

Table 4.1 shows the socio-demographic data of respondents. The results showed that 126(30.0%) of the respondents were aged 12-17 years and 294(70.0%) were aged 18-20 years. About 238(56.7%) of the respondents were males while 182(43.3%) were females. For place of residence, 212(50.5%) lived in Yenagoa, 150(35.7%) lived in the village while 58(13.8%) lived at the water front. For students class of study, 183(43.6%) were in SS1, 179(42.6%) SS2 and 58(13.8%) SS3. For religion, 210(50.0%) were Christians, 150(35.7%) were Islam while 60(14.3%) indicated Traditional African Religion.

Research question 1: *What is the influence of age as a predictor to non-consensual sex experiences among senior secondary school students in Bayelsa State?*

Table 4.2: Age and non-consensual sex experiences

Variables	Non-Consensual Sex Experiences		Total Freq (%)
	Yes Freq (%)	No Freq (%)	
Age			
12 – 17	95(75.4)	31(24.6)	126(100)
18 – 20	58(19.7)	236(80.3)	294(100)
Total	153(36.4)	267(63.6)	420(100)

Table 4.2 shows the influence of age as a predictor to non-consensual sex experiences among senior secondary school students in Bayelsa State. The result showed that 95(75.4%) of the respondents aged 12-17 years and 58(19.7%) aged 18-20 years experienced non-consensual sex.

Research question 2: *What is the influence of gender as a predictor to non-consensual sex experiences among senior secondary school students in Bayelsa State?*

Table 4.3: Gender and non-consensual sex experiences

Variables	Non-Consensual Sex Experiences		Total Freq (%)
	Yes Freq (%)	No Freq (%)	
Gender			
Male	32(13.4)	206(86.6)	238(100)
Female	121(66.5)	61(33.5)	182(100)
Total	153(36.4)	267(63.6)	420(100)

Table 4.3 shows the influence of gender as a predictor to non-consensual sex experiences among senior secondary school students in Bayelsa State. The result showed that 32(13.4%) of the respondents who were males and 121(66.5%) who were females experienced non-consensual sex.

Research question 3: *What is the influence of peer pressure as a predictor to non-consensual sex experiences among senior secondary school students in Bayelsa State?*

Table 4.4: Peer pressure and experiences of non-consensual sex

Variables	Non-Consensual Sex Experiences		Total Freq (%)
	Yes Freq (%)	No Freq (%)	
Peer Pressure			
Pressure	153(46.2)	178(53.8)	331(100)
Not pressured	0(0.0)	89(100)	89(100)
Total	153(36.4)	267(63.6)	420(100)

Table 4.4 shows the influence of peer pressure as a predictor to non-consensual sex experiences among senior secondary school students in Bayelsa State. The result showed that 153(46.2%) of the respondents who were pressured experienced non-consensual sex.

Research question 4: *What is the influence of place of residence as a predictor to non-consensual sex experiences among senior secondary school students in Bayelsa State?*

Table 4.5: Place of residence and non-consensual sex experiences

Variables	Non-Consensual Sex Experiences		Total Freq (%)
	Yes Freq (%)	No Freq (%)	
Place of Residence			
Yenagoa	92(43.4)	120(56.6)	212(100)
Village	61(40.7)	89(59.3)	150(100)
Water Front	0(0.0)	58(100)	58(100)
Total	153(36.4)	267(63.6)	420(100)

Table 4.5 shows the influence of place of residence as a predictor to non-consensual sex experiences among senior secondary school students in Bayelsa State. The result showed that 92(43.4%) of the respondents who lived in Yenagoa, 61(40.7%) who lived in the village experienced non-consensual sex. Research question 5: What is the influence of student’s class as a predictor to non-consensual sex experiences among senior secondary school in Bayelsa State.?

Table 4.6: Students class and non-consensual sex experiences

Variables	Non-Consensual Sex Experiences		Total Freq (%)
	Yes Freq (%)	No Freq (%)	
Class			
SS1	33(18.0)	150(82.0)	183(100)
SS2	91(50.8)	88(49.2)	179(100)
SS3	29(50.0)	29(50.0)	58(100)
Total	153(36.4)	267(63.6)	420(100)

Table 4.6 shows the influence of student’s class as a predictor to non-consensual sex experiences among senior secondary school students in Bayelsa State. The result showed that 33(18.0%) of the respondents who were in SS1, 91(50.8%) in SS2 and 29(50.0%) in SS3 experienced non-consensual sex. Research question 6: What is the influence of religion as a predictor to non-consensual sex experiences among senior secondary school students in Bayelsa State.?

Table 4.7: Religion and non-consensual sex experiences

Variables	Non-Consensual Sex Experiences		Total Freq (%)
	Yes Freq (%)	No Freq (%)	
Religion			
Christianity	120(57.1)	90(42.9)	210(100)
Islam	33(22.0)	117(78.0)	150(100)
Traditional African Religion	0(0.0)	60(100)	60(100)
Total	153(36.4)	267(63.6)	420(100)

Table 4.7 shows the influence of religion as a predictor to non-consensual sex experiences among senior secondary school students in Bayelsa State. The result showed that 120(57.1%) of the respondents who were Christians and 33(22.0%) experienced non-consensual sex. Research question 7: What is the influence of sexual orientation as a predictor to experiences of non-consensual sex among senior secondary school students in Bayelsa State?

Table 4.8: Sexual orientation and non-consensual sex experiences

Variables	Non-Consensual Sex Experiences		Total Freq (%)
	Yes Freq (%)	No Freq (%)	
Sexual orientation			
Yes	91(33.8)	178(66.2)	269(100)
No	62(41.1)	89(58.9)	151(100)
Total	153(36.4)	267(63.6)	420(100)

Table 4.8 shows the influence of sexual orientation as a predictor to non-consensual sex experiences among senior secondary school students in Bayelsa State. The result showed that 91(33.8%) of the respondents who sexual orientation and 62(41.1%) who never had sexual orientation experienced non-consensual sex.

Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between age and experiences of non-consensual sex among senior secondary schools students in Bayelsa State.

Table 4.9: Pearson Correlation showing significant relationship between age and experiences of non-consensual sex among senior secondary schools students in Bayelsa State

Variables		Non-consensual sex	Age	Decision
Non-consensual sex	Correlation	1	0.53 0.00*	H ₀ rejected
	N	420	420	
Age	Correlation	0.53 0.00*	1	
	N	420	420	

*Significant; p<0.05

Table 4.9 showed the Pearson Correlation of relationship between age and experiences of non-consensual sex among senior secondary schools students in Bayelsa State. The result indicated that there is a significant relationship (N = 420; r = 0.53; p<0.05). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there was no significant relationship between age and experiences of non-consensual sex among senior secondary schools students in Bayelsa State was rejected.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between gender and experiences of non-consensual sex among senior secondary schools students in Bayelsa State.

Table 4.10: Pearson Correlation showing significant relationship between gender and experiences of non-consensual sex among senior secondary schools students in Bayelsa State

Variables		Non-consensual sex	Gender	Decision
Non-consensual sex	Correlation	1	0.54 0.00*	H ₀ rejected
	N	420	420	
Gender	Correlation	0.54 0.00*	1	
	N	420	420	

*Significant; p<0.05

Table 4.10 showed the Pearson Correlation of relationship between gender and experiences of non-consensual sex among senior secondary schools students in Bayelsa State. The result indicated that there is a significant relationship (N = 420; r = 0.54; p<0.05). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there was no significant relationship between gender and experiences of non-consensual sex among senior secondary schools students in Bayelsa State was rejected.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between peer pressure and experiences of non-consensual sex among senior secondary schools students in Bayelsa State.

Table 4.11: Pearson Correlation showing significant relationship between peer pressure and experiences of non-consensual sex among senior secondary schools students in Bayelsa State

Variables		Non-consensual sex	Peer pressure	Decision
Non-consensual sex	Correlation	1	0.39 0.00*	H ₀ rejected
	N	420	420	
Peer pressure	Correlation	0.39 0.00*	1	
	N	420	420	

*Significant; p<0.05

Table 4.10 showed the Pearson Correlation of relationship between peer pressure and experiences of non-consensual sex among senior secondary schools students in Bayelsa State. The result indicated that there was a significant relationship (N = 420; r = 0.39; p<0.05). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between peer pressure and experiences of non-consensual sex among senior secondary schools students in Bayelsa State was rejected.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant relationship between place of residence and experiences of non-consensual sex among senior secondary schools students in Bayelsa State.

Table 4.12: Pearson Correlation showing significant relationship between place of residence and experiences of non-consensual sex among senior secondary schools students in Bayelsa State

Variables		Non-consensual sex	Place of residence	Decision
Non-consensual sex	Correlation	1	0.24 0.00*	H ₀ rejected
	N	420	420	
Place of residence	Correlation	0.24 0.00*	1	
	N	420	420	

*Significant; p<0.05

Table 4.11 showed the Pearson Correlation of relationship between place of residence and experiences of non-consensual sex among senior secondary schools students in Bayelsa State. The result indicated that there was a significant relationship (N = 420; r = 0.24; p<0.05). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between place of residence and experiences of non-consensual sex among senior secondary schools students in Bayelsa State was rejected.

Hypothesis 5: There is no significant relationship between student's class and experiences of non-consensual sex among senior secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Table 4.13: Pearson Correlation showing significant relationship between student's class and experiences of non-consensual sex among senior secondary schools students in Bayelsa State

Variables		Non-consensual sex	Student's class	Decision
Non-consensual sex	Correlation	1	0.29 0.00*	H ₀ rejected
	N	420	420	
Student's class	Correlation	0.29 0.00*	1	
	N	420	420	

*Significant; p<0.05

Table 4.13 showed the Pearson Correlation of relationship between student's class and experiences of non-consensual sex among senior secondary schools students in Bayelsa State. The result indicated that there was a significant relationship (N = 420; r = 0.29; p<0.05). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between student's class and experiences of non-consensual sex among senior secondary schools students in Bayelsa State was rejected.

Hypothesis 6: There is no significant relationship between religion and experiences of non-consensual sex among senior secondary schools students in Bayelsa State.

Table 4.14: Pearson Correlation showing significant relationship between religion and experiences of non-consensual sex among senior secondary schools students in Bayelsa State

Variables		Non-consensual sex	Religion	Decision
Non-consensual sex	Correlation	1	0.45 0.00*	H ₀ rejected
	N	420	420	
Religion	Correlation	0.45 0.00*	1	
	N	420	420	

*Significant; p<0.05

Table 4.14 showed the Pearson Correlation of relationship between religion and experiences of non-consensual sex among senior secondary schools students in Bayelsa State. The result indicated that there was a significant relationship (N = 420; r = 0.45; p<0.05). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between religion and experiences of non-consensual sex among senior secondary schools students in Bayelsa State was rejected.

Hypothesis 7: There is no significant relationship between sexual orientation and experiences of non-consensual sex among senior secondary schools students in Bayelsa State.

Table 4.15: Pearson Correlation showing significant relationship between sexual orientation and experiences of non-consensual sex among senior secondary schools students in Bayelsa State

Variables		Non-consensual sex	Sexual orientation	Decision
Non-consensual sex	Correlation	1	0.72 0.00*	H ₀ rejected
	N	420	420	
Sexual orientation	Correlation	0.72 0.00*	1	
	N	420	420	

*Significant; p<0.05

Table 4.15 showed the Pearson Correlation of relationship between sexual orientation and experiences of non-consensual sex among senior secondary schools students in Bayelsa State. The result indicated that there was a significant relationship (N = 420; r = 0.72; p<0.05). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between sexual orientation and experiences of non-consensual sex among senior secondary schools students in Bayelsa State was rejected.

DISCUSSION

The results showed the influence of age as a predictor to non-consensual sex experiences among senior secondary school students in Bayelsa State. The result showed that 95(75.4%) of the respondents aged 12-17 years and 58(19.7%) aged 18-20 years experienced non-consensual sex. This implies that younger students experienced more non-consensual sex, this was expected as older aged adolescents are usually more bold and can resist unwanted sexual contacts more compared to the younger ones. The result of this study agreed with that of Aboul et al. (2012) which had an overall prevalence rate for child sexual abuse of 29.8% and the average age of child sexual abuse for males was 9.20 years, compared to 10.03 years for female victims, this was supported by Ybarra and Mitchell (2013) which showed that 9% of youths reported unwanted sex and the 16 years old was the modal age of first sexual perpetration (n = 18 [40%]) with mean age at first perpetration to be 16.2. According to Durowade et al. (2017), the prevalence of

early sexual debut was about 11%. The mean age of sexual debut was 13.10 ± 2.82 ; the mean age for early sexual debutants was 11.68 ± 1.98 . The reviewed studies show non-consensual sex is more common among the younger aged bracket. To buttress this findings, Sivertsen et al. (2019) showed that all forms of non-consensual sex experienced during the previous year were significantly more common in the youngest age cohort; 19.4% of those aged 18-20, 18.1% (21-22years), 16.4% (23-25years, 4.3% (26-28 years) and 9.3% (29-35years) reported any form of non-consensual sex. The reduction in the prevalence of non-consensual sex with age may be due to the older youths ability to resist sexual advances or on the other extreme is a perception that sexual assault is a norm and they no longer view sexual encounters as non-consensual, this change in perception can happen due to repeated sexual assaults until the victims accept their fate or even begin to enjoy the exploitation and it's a psychological problem. However, Mezie-okoye, et, al., (2014) showed that age was not significantly associated with sexual violence ($p=0.85$, $OR=0.96$, $CI=0.63-1.41$) and non-consensual sex occurred equally across all age bracket, other factors may be responsible for this result such as peer pressure, societal expectations and poor socioeconomic conditions.

The results showed the influence of gender as a predictor to non-consensual sex experiences among senior secondary school students in Bayelsa State. The result showed that 32(13.4%) of the respondents who were males and 121(66.5%) who were females experienced non-consensual sex. This implies that more females experienced non-consensual sex compared to males. This was expected as historically females have been the target of sexual assault for multiple reasons that cut across traditional perception of women's roles, socioeconomic disparities between males and females in Africa, the physical strength and the higher sexual libido of the males. The findings of this study was supported by several other studies such as that of Aboul et al. (2012) where the overall prevalence rate for child sexual abuse was 29.8%, with rates being higher for females (37.8%) than for males (21.2%), results from Olamide et al. (2012) indicated that 11.8% of females had suffered rape at the hands of their date, also Sivertsen et al., (2019) showed 24.2% of students reported non-consensual sex and 16.7% reported having been harassed within the past year, the findings also showed that women reported substantially more non-consensual sex than men (lifetime: 31.3% vs. 8.0%) and same gender effect was observed for the previous year (21.6% vs. 5.7%). Abe (2012) stated that more female perceived non-consensual sex to be persistent unwanted pressure, physical and sexual advances (75% female and 25 % male). A greater number and percentage of females indicated that they had experienced sexually harassing behavior in the three categories; 85%, 81% and 9% percent in physical, verbal and sexual assault respectively. Fewer males (23%) indicated that they have experienced physical and verbal harassment, while none reported sexual assault.

The reviewed studies all indicate that females experience more non-consensual sex compared to men, several studies indicated that females are more exposed to rape, for instance, Carey et al. (2015) revealed that 18% of the females reported incapacitated rape (IR) before entering college, and 15% reported forcible rape (FR). During the first year of college, 15% reported IR and 9% reported FR. The lifetime prevalence reported being 26% and 22% for IR and FR respectively. Also Ezechi et al., (2016) indicated a steady increase in the proportion of reported cases of sexual violence over the years ($P < 0.0001$). Sexual assaults were recorded among the males (6.1%), although female victims were in the majority (93.9%). More studies recorded cases of non-consensual sexual relations such as Arulogun et al. (2013) where 58% of respondents (20% male, 80% female) reported experiencing sexual harassment at some point in their lives. 1298 adolescents participated in the study by Gabriel-Job, (2019) where 462 (35.6%) had experienced sexual abuse. The victims consisted of 176(38.1%) males and 286 (61.9%) females. ($c^2=12.02$, $p < 0.001$). Gender was significantly associated with penetrative ($p=0.006$, $OR=1.74$, $CI=1.15-2.64$) and contact with no penetrative ($p<0.001$, $ROR=2.42$, $CI=0.26-0.64$) forms of sexual abuse. The studies by Desouky and Marawan, (2013), Oni et al. (2019) and Ybarra et al. (2012) all showed unwanted sexual experience was more common among females and some specific issues of sexual harassment included unwanted touching, kissing, suggestive messages, seductive looks and rape. Elgazzar et al. (2020) revealed that gender of victim was significantly related to delayed disclosure as females were less likely to report sexual harassment compared to males. The similarity in the reviewed studies can be linked

to several factors cutting across socioeconomic, religious and cultural that exposes females more to non-consensual sex.

The results showed the influence of peer pressure as a predictor to non-consensual sex experiences among senior secondary school students in Bayelsa State. The result showed that 153(46.2%) of the respondents who were pressured experienced non-consensual sex. This implies peer pressure was a strong predictor of non-consensual sex. This result aligns with the study of Imaledo et al. (2012) which showed more than (32.9%) of the respondents were of the view that it is not proper for a man to report if he is forced to have sex by his girlfriend. 23.1% were of the view that non-consensual sex is part of relationship so it should be tolerated. According to Rakhi et al. (2014) sexual resilience was significantly correlated with attitude towards partner pressure. Having friends who engaged in sexual activities was associated with early sexual exposure ($p < 0.05$) (Durowade, et al., 2017), and according to Taiwo et al. (2014) bad influence (3%) are all various reasons responsible for continuous perpetration of non-consensual sex in the institutions studied. The similarities in the result may be because peer pressure influences ones perception and attitude towards non-consensual sex, as most youths now view non-consensual sex as a normal part of life and not a good reason to seek help.

The results showed the influence of place of residence as a predictor to non-consensual sex experiences among senior secondary school students in Bayelsa State. The result showed that 92(43.4%) of the respondents who lived in Yenagoa, 61(40.7%) who lived in the village experienced non-consensual sex. This means more urban dwellers had non-consensual sex compared to village dwellers, although the difference is minimal and not significant. The probable reason may be because the study had more urban population residents. This study findings did not align with the that of Aboul et al. (2012) which showed the prevalence of non-consensual sex was higher in rural than urban residency. Also Farahat et al. (2020) showed those who were rural residents were exposed to non-consensual sex more frequently than those of urban residence (69.4%, $X^2 = 35.85$, $P < 0.001$). Giving an explanation for this result, the study stated that the faculty existed in the rural sector, this big exposure to non-consensual sex may be attributed to the feeling that the harassed female students are outsiders and hence there is no family protection layer for them in contrast to urban ones. The disparity in the prevalence of non-consensual sex between urban and rural dwellers may be due to the difference in the socioeconomic standards of the residents as lower socioeconomic standard is directly correlated with an increased prevalence of non-consensual sex, this was buttressed by Iwunna et al. (2022) which indicated that there was a significant association between socio-economic status and sexual abuse among adolescents in Gokana Local Government Area of Rivers State ($p < 0.05$). The difference between this study and the reviewed studies may be because this study had more urban population residents.

The results showed the influence of student's class as a predictor to non-consensual sex experiences among senior secondary school students in Bayelsa State. The result showed that 33(18.0%) of the respondents who were in SS1, 91(50.8%) in SS2 and 29(50.0%) in SS3 experienced non-consensual sex. This implies students in SS2 were most engaged in non-consensual sex, this may be due to the combination of hormonal factors and peer pressure that students face at this period of time. This result was confirmed by the study of Chime et al. (2021) which showed predictors of child sexual assault was students in senior secondary school Class 2 (SSS2). Most students in lower classes experience more non-consensual sex as revealed by Carey et al. (2015) study that revealed, 18% of the respondents reported incapacitated rape (IR) before entering college, and 15% reported forcible rape (FR). During the first year of college, 15% reported IR and 9% reported FR. Also Samuel and Elijah (2018) showed secondary school students in Rivers State had positive perception towards non-consensual sex, perception of non-consensual sex differed among respondents based on age (10-14 years, mean 22.63, SD:5.72) which is equivalent to junior secondary and (15 and above, mean 19.33, SD:5.05) equivalent to senior secondary. This was also supported by Mezie-okoye et al. (2014) which revealed most of the victims 64.3% had their first experience of sexual violence in their first year of study; 23.8% in 200 level, 6.7% in 300 level and 5.2% in the 400 level. The similarities may be due to factors like peer pressure.

The results showed the influence of religion as a predictor to non-consensual sex experiences among senior secondary school students in Bayelsa State. The result showed that 120(57.1%) of the respondents who were Christians and 33(22.0%) of Muslims experienced non-consensual sex. This implies more Christians experience non-consensual sex, although this may be because the population are predominantly Christians. The findings of this study does not align with that of Amy and Brittany (2012) in a cross-national study that showed Muslims report more conservative attitudes about sex than do most other religious adherents. Most major religions discourage sex outside of marriage, but some religions appear more effective than others at curtailing sexual behavior. According to Danielle (2021), those who experienced rape experienced significantly greater change in their religious belief compared to those who had not been raped and those who experienced trauma other than rape ($p = .015$).

The results showed the influence of sexual orientation as a predictor to non-consensual sex experiences among senior secondary school students in Bayelsa State. The result showed that 91(33.8%) of the respondents who had sexual orientation and 62(41.1%) who never had sexual orientation experienced non-consensual sex. This implies that those who never had sexual orientation experienced more non-consensual sex. This is in line with the study of Vasileia and Karasavva (2021) which showed 13.7% of the participants had at some point in their life, distributed nude, or sexual pictures of someone else without consent and 28.5% had experienced such victimization and non-consensual intimate image perpetration was predictive of non-Consensual intimate image victimization and vice versa. According to Imaledo et al. (2012), more than (32.9%) of the respondents were of the view that it is not proper for a man to report if he is forced to have sex by his girlfriend. 23.1% were of the view that non-consensual sex is part of relationship so it should be tolerated. 22% of respondents agreed that their first sexual experience was non-consensual. Urada et al. (2019) stated that those who reported sexual abuse were more likely to be involved in pornography before age 18. An experimental study conducted by Zafar and Inayat, (2014) using an ambiguous non-consensual sex scenario indicate that while female students perceived the scenario as more sexually harassing than male students, however, both men and women judged female perpetrators less harshly than male perpetrators. Both men and women were affected by perpetrator attractiveness: they perceived an attractive opposite gender perpetrator as less harassing than a same gender attractive perpetrator. Omorogiuwa (2018) and Suleiman (2017) showed that dress attitude, lack of respect for opposite sex as factors responsible for non-consensual sex. The reviewed studies indicate that giving proper sexual orientation to teenagers is important in reducing the occurrence of non-consensual sex.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that younger age, female gender, peer pressure, place of residence, class, religion and sexual orientation are important predictors of non-consensual sex. Therefore, there is need to put in place special programmes that will address the perception and attitude towards non-consensual sex among young ones.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In view of the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made.

1. The government should conduct a thorough contextual analysis to identify factors influencing non-consensual sex among public secondary school students in Bayelsa State.
2. The government through the ministry of education should create, evidence-based curriculum that addresses fundamental aspects of sex education with emphasis on abstinence, reproductive rights and negotiation skills in Bayelsa State .
3. Non-governmental organizations should establish collaborative partnerships with school authorities in the implementation of health education programs and sex education be incorporated into the existing school curricular activities.
4. The ministry of health should engage parents and the community in promoting safe sex awareness by organizing workshops, seminars, and community outreach programs to educate parents about

reinforcing moral values at home and foster a sense of shared responsibility for the well-being of students.

5. Head of schools should leverage peer group discussion forums to enhance discussion about the topic of sex education in a controlled environment and provide materials that are user-friendly, and aligned with the moral values available in Bayelsa State.
6. The laws concerning non-consensual sex be emphasized, intensified, enforced and offenders should be punishment in line with the ambits of the law.

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